

The Aesthetics in Design and Cultural Studies

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Abstract: Discussing aesthetics as an aspect of design touches upon one of the most vital matters of how design functions as a means of communication.

Especially in non-professional contexts, when design artifacts are noticed and appreciated, it is more often for their *aesthetic* qualities than their practical or functional ability to solve more or less complex or well-defined problems. Furthermore, working with aesthetics is often regarded as a core competence in design, and the pervasive attention paid to aesthetics can be annoying to designers, as it implies that they work solely with artistic matters of surface, appearance, and styling as opposed to, for example, functionality.

The theoretical framework proposed here can be used in analyses and discussions of aesthetics in design, but it can also inform designers who need to deal practically with the challenges of the aesthetic in design. The two aspects of aesthetics in design that are put forward in this paper—design as a structure of sensual appearance, and design as an act of communication that may contain an aesthetic coding that lets an idea or content of meaning be physically manifested and reflected in different ways—can lead to a more theoretically focused inclusion of aesthetic matters in the process of designing.

Keywords: *design, aesthetics, communication and experience.*

Introduction

Aesthetics in design has been a neglected area of research, even though there has been some attention given to understanding the aesthetic qualities of the non-functional, “emotional” factors in design. [1,2]. Attempts to establish a scientific discourse for design have instead placed emphasis on analyzing and prescribing the *methodology* in designing (as in the practice-based framework of Design Methods) [3,4,5]; or the impact of *culture* and social processes on the making and consumption of design (as in studies of design history and the material culture of design, where matters of aesthetics are often consciously set aside due to an ideological struggle with the pervading notion of “good design” and its prescriptive aesthetics of outer beauty leading to moral improvement) [6,7]; or the issue of *meaning* in design—that is, how “form follows meaning”—and how design, on a semantic basis, makes sense in different contexts (e.g. contexts of use, language, life cycle, and ecology) [8, 9] . All of these positions have more or less left out any analytical consideration of aesthetics. However, raising the issue of aesthetics in design is crucial, and not doing so leads to diffuse and sometimes unqualified discussions.

This paper, will establish a conceptual Framework for discussing, theorizing, analyzing, and practically addressing aesthetics in design. It presents mainly the theory of phenomenology but also touch upon various aspects of the tradition of aesthetic theory in European philosophy. The paper aim is, however, not to use a philosophical, conceptual discourse to establish the "true" meaning of the word "aesthetic" to define it once and for all. The history of the concept itself has led in many directions—it was coined by Alexander Baumgarten in *Aesthetica* (1750–58) to describe a philosophical discipline that investigates the "lower" sensual aspects of human experience as opposed to the higher realm of logics. This led to the debate on taste and value judgment of beauty and the sublime in Kant's *Critique of Judgment* (1790) [10], which preceded the close link between the work of art and the philosophy of aesthetics from Schelling's Romantic-idealistic celebration of the work of art in *Philosophy of Art* (1802) to Adorno's Modern-critical investigations of the communicative means and utopian potential of art in *Aesthetic Theory* (1970). [11]

The paper's aim is to a new understanding of aesthetics in design will not go through the traditional discussions of art as a medium of aesthetic appreciation and communication, as this risks reducing design to a matter and medium of artistic aspiration. A design object can be the result of purely artistic and autonomous self-expression, but it often has a wider context. In relation to design methodology, it will be more justified to speak of design as a meeting point of multiple interests (those of a client, designer, and manufacturer) and as a complex negotiation between "problem formulation" and "solution generation." [12, 13] From a point of view of cultural analysis, design is a practice of innovation and change, not to be separated from the culturally circumscribed patterns of consumption. Further, an appropriation of design by the aesthetics of art, implying a view of design as art, may hamper an understanding of the unique complexity of almost every design object or solution: that design is not the expression of a lone artist, but the result of commercial and societal processes [14] and, at best, of an ambition to grasp the potential power of giving shape to our environments in innovative and progressive ways that are appropriate to human needs.

Aesthetics is no longer the exclusive domain of art but applies to our immediate, sensuous experience of the world. To demonstrate these points, it will be examined two examples: interior designs by the British Iraqi deconstructivist architect, Zaha Hadid and various designs of chairs by the Egyptian designer Karim Rashid.

1. Form and Sensuous Experience

Evaluating aesthetics in design is mainly a matter of grasping its sensuous qualities, or, rather, design's distinctive appeals to the senses. This does not mean that assessing aesthetic qualities in design exhausts all the different properties that design encompasses (for example, functionality and sustainability). [15] The purpose here is to explore how form and appearance can be qualified as means of a type of aesthetic communication that challenges experience, and to discuss the role of form as a challenge to our understanding of things.

These issues of form, experience, and understanding in design can be situated within two powerful frameworks. First of all, in recent years there has been a tendency to try to loosen the connection between art and aesthetic theory, and, to revisit Baumgarten's original idea of applying aesthetics to sensual matter

(in Old Greek, *aisthetá*, "that which can be sensed"). This movement from Works of art to general sensuous experience and, further, to questions concerning how reality is arranged and perceived aesthetically, is the topic of a new era of aesthetic theory that has been unfolding since the 1990's in works by philosophers Richard Schusterman, [16] Martin Seel, [17] and Gernot Böhme. [18] Tellingly, the title of one of Böhme's recent works features the Greek root of the word aesthetics: *Aisthethik*.

Second, this bias of recent aesthetic theory can be seen in the contextualization of phenomenology as a philosophy that addresses the fundamental premise of the importance of experience and the basic conditions of experience. The term "phenomenology" was coined by the philosopher Edmund Husserl based on Old Greek etymology as the doctrine (*logos*) of that which shows itself (*phainomenon*). The point is that phenomenology, as a theory of experience, can address certain aspects of aesthetics related to sensuous appearance and experience. In the following, the paper will use the theory of the French phenomenologist Maurice Merleau-Ponty to discuss various modes of sensual qualities in design. In an important essay, "L'entrelacs—Le chiasme," [19] Merleau-Ponty introduces two kinds of interlaced structures in experience to which it will be referred in the following discussion of two important aspects of aesthetics in design.

1.1.An Aesthetics of Sensual Relation

Merleau-Ponty's first structure takes its departure in immediate and concrete experience. Here, Merleau-Ponty follows a basic assumption in phenomenology: That experience is a matter for a concrete and specific subject whose consciousness is incarnated in a body that is located in a concrete world of things and intersubjective relations.

Reversely, the "world" is only ever a matter for a bodily incarnated subject. Merleau-Ponty criticizes the traditional dichotomy of subject and object. Further, in a sort of deconstructive gesture he attempts to reverse the dichotomy in order to show that it has a common foundation in a figure of continuity that he calls the *flesh*, "la chair." He speaks of density of the flesh ("l'épaisseur de chair") as a means of communication between the viewer and the thing.

For Merleau-Ponty: "The body participates in the order of things and likewise the world is universal flesh." [20] Experience, in Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology, is an ongoing exchange between subject and object that takes place in the common material of "chair."

Almost as an explication of Merleau-Ponty's notion of "chair," the German philosopher Gernot Böhme has developed a powerful concept of ambience, *Atmosphäre*, to analyze how things, situations, and surroundings appeal to us. The point is that ambience can only evolve if there is an experiencing subject [21]. However, it is not an inherent part of the subject but rather objective as the result of an effect evoked by a specific constellation of things. [22] Thus, to Böhme the concept of ambience becomes the main designator for the conditions of perception, the "primary object for perception": [23] and even though they are not characteristics of the objects, they are obviously produced through the characteristics and interplay of objects. That is, ambiances are something *between* subject and object. They are not something relational; they are the relation itself. . . .it is the ambience the first reality of perception out of which subject and object can be separated. [24]

In this context, three aspects of Böhme's theory are particularly important:

- First, as a theory of sensuous experience and relation, to Böhme the main concern of aesthetics is how ambience works and constitutes a specific relation between subject and object: "For aesthetics, the ambiances are therefore the first and essential reality. They are the perceptible co-existence of subject and object." [25]

In Böhme's perspective, there might be a "real reality" behind the operations of ambience, but what is important for aesthetics is the "reality of appearance" which puts an emphasis on how (perception of) "reality" is mediated through ambience, on the effect of surface and form, and on the value of staging meaning. [26]

- Second, ambience is experienced and expresses itself as a coherent unit. Instead separating the various aspects of sensuous experience (i.e., sight, hearing, scent, etc.) and asking how one sense can evoke effects in another, ambience functions as the perceptual background upon which things and surroundings present themselves, and where one may look for sensuous differentiation. In this context, Böhme discusses the traditional aesthetic concept of synaesthesia and especially the power of colour. [27]

- And, third, ambience is not only something to be experienced but also something to be *made*, or manipulated. Böhme speaks of "aesthetic work," the intention of giving things, surroundings, and people certain qualities that let them appear as something special with a power of appeal to be perceived in a certain (controlled) way. [28] In this context, he mentions creative areas such as stage work, commercials, art, architecture, and design as examples. This notion of aesthetic work is clearly linked to today's prevalent concept of experience economy [29] and to the way in which our surroundings—especially with the help of design—can be seen as "aesthetically calculated," where the artifacts in question are conceived with a high degree of "aestheticity," construed to be perceived "aesthetically." [30]

2. Design as a Structure of Appearance

The strength of Merleau-Ponty's phenomenological and Böhme's aesthetic-philosophical framework is that they conceptualize the relation of sensual experience between subjective apprehension and objective appearance. Merleau-Ponty thus follows the phenomenological dogma of reducing the world of phenomena to abstract in order to investigate the basic structure of experience in itself. Böhme, on the other hand, through the notion of ambience, seeks to conceptualize the importance of the *specific* world we encounter, but in the end, he too remains in the realm of abstract speculation through his main philosophical interest in issues of, for example, the notion of perception. [31] In dealing with an increasingly designed and aesthetically staged world, we need more precise concepts to discuss the structure of appearance. In relation to this, in a philosophical, cultural, and material context, design is important as a major means of structuring the appearance and the surface that signifies "world" in our perception and cognition. An example of an important design is the Future Faucet Design by Zaha Hadid. This is elegant design of kooky faucet. The faucet component design is ones for filtered water, controlled by a touch-sensitive button, and the other is for unfiltered hot and cold water. Some of us think this fantastic faucet looks like a metallic swan from another planet. This is the best future faucet winner the Pritzker Prize (Figure 1). The question, then, is how the world of (designed) objects in general influences

Figure 1 Hadid's Future Faucet Design, 2010

the modality of the experiencing subject. [32]

As an example of a kind of design that creates an ambience and thus stages a certain kind of relation between subject and object, it is present the interior design created by Zaha Hadid. [20] Interior design often evokes a high aesthetic effect of ambience because it is capable of creating an encapsulating and highly calculated environment. This is certainly the case in Hadid's new chamber music hall Manchester Art Gallery (2009, Figure 2), her interior design for Vitra Fire Station (1994, Figure 3), and her (kitchen in Figure 4). Hadid's projects shows design at its extreme, rethinking and reshaping our conception and perception of the environment. [33] Hadid not only creates a certain ambient space that suspends the traditional organization of space; she intensifies this ambience. In the words of Judy Attfield, Hadid's spaces enable a kind of "aesthetic perception," that not only invests itself in the immediate appearance—a key word for Seel—of the world, in the sense that the world is given to us as "a momentary and simultaneous abundance of appearance," but also intensifies the appearance of the pure present that is otherwise inaccessible to ordinary perception". [34] Thus, to Seel, aesthetic perception is a matter of looking in a certain intent way that involves attention for the play of appearances. The focus is still on the given objects, which are simply seen in another way, that is, with an enhanced sense of the presence of the situation. [35]

The argument in this context is that Hadid's design points reflectively to itself and urges a kind of "aesthetic perception," apparently "wanting" to be perceived with an enhanced sense of presence, of being in exactly this ambience, here and now, and achieving exactly this through "designerly" and sensuous means such as colour, materials, and form. By combining these means into a whole, one can create not only ambience but also a reflective space that questions how space is perceived.

Figure 2 Hadid's new chamber music hall, Manchester Art Gallery, 2009

2.1. An Aesthetics of Communicative Self-reflection

Merleau-Ponty's second interlaced structure is also bound to concrete experience but has to do with the way in which every concrete, visible manifestation carries with it an invisible idea or meaning.

He speaks of a bond “of the flesh and the idea, of the visible and the *inner brace* that the visible makes “manifest and hides,” meaning that the idea is not the contrary of the sensual but instead it *double* and its *depth*. [36] An additional point is that the idea, though always a part of the sensual, cannot reach the surface of direct manifestation; instead it operates as a “transparency behind the sensible.” [37] It is about this structure that the paper investigates the context of aesthetics and design. In the same way that the sensuous relation of an appealing objects and a sensitive subject can be called aesthetic. That Merleau-Ponty's notion of incarnated ideas can be applied to design is obvious: every piece of design contains an idea, a dimension of immateriality; vice versa, design is only conceivable as something concretely manifested— when speaking of immaterial design, Merleau-Ponty's structure of interlaced meaning indicates that it is nothing without some sort of physical manifestation. This could be considered a matter of *communication*, that is, specifically, how the relation of manifestation/idea displays itself in design. Whereas the question up till now has been how design establishes a sensuous relation with a perceiving and experiencing subject, the question now relates to the object itself, asking how the object in its sensual being points to a level of idea content or meaning, which, in a complex process of displacement, it

Figure 3 Hadid's Interior design of Vitra Fire Station (1994), Weil am Rhein, Germany

Figure 4 Hadid's Kitchen at Guggenheim's exhibition New York (2006)

simultaneously contains and conceals. [38] This aesthetic operation could be considered in two ways:

- First, it unfolds through the sensual being of an object, which links it to the aesthetics of the sensual relation.

- Second, the relation of physical manifestation and idea, which can be more or less direct and more or less problematic, has also been a topic of modern, art-based aesthetic theory. The question has been how the work of art is constituted through a specific "form" that (un)reveals its meaning and/or resists understanding. [39] In the following, it will be focused this aspect under the heading of *aesthetic coding*, which examines how an object can not only attract attention and appeal to the senses (as in the sensual relation) but also be constituted in a way where it, in establishing a specific relation of physical manifestation/idea, demands or even commands a specific order of alignment or mode of understanding. Jakobson speaks of a self-reflective "poetic function," which in focusing on the act of communication itself could be more or less activated within language, thus proposing "poetic language" to have a dominance of poetic function. [40] Thus, we can speak of objects with a high degree of "aestheticity," that is, with an implicit, communicative construction those points in this direction.

3. The Concept of Added Quality in Aesthetic Objects

How aesthetic objects contain something "more" has been a central topic of modern, art-based theory, from Schelling to Adorno. The ability to articulate this aspect has been one of the major benefits of this kind of theory and is far from obsolete today, although it may at one time have been too narrowly focused on art. Besides, it holds considerable potential for criticism of the operations and contexts of aesthetic phenomena—something that has been sorely neglected by the aesthetic theory directly related to design. Thus, in his influential *Aesthetic Theory*, Adorno discusses art as a medium that paradoxically is inevitably bound to the reality of the given, while at the same time having the potential to transcend the given. He says that "phantasy" cannot be "that cheap ability to escape being in proposing a non-being as if it existed"; instead it can transform "what the works of art always absorbed from being, into constellations, through which they become the other of being, is it also only through the specific negation of being." [41]

Martin Seel claims that art's ability is to "bring forward otherwise unrepresentable circumstances. "Art, in his view, has to do with: "...ways of human commitment in the real or the unreal, in conditions of the world in the past, the present, or the future. Objects of art are medium for an experience that takes place as a process of an understanding that isn't oriented towards a result of an understood...Understanding art is more about an otherwise impossible meeting with otherwise impossible possibilities of perceiving ourselves. [42]

As objects of everyday life, it may perhaps be difficult to see design in this context of an aesthetic negation of reality and proposals of new models of understanding. Still, though, it is worth asking designed objects the difficult question concerning how they define a relation to reality in the relation of physical manifestation/idea, and how they can be seen as mediums for meeting the world in new and/or reflective ways where new kinds of experience and of experiencing are evoked.

In the case of Hadid, the conceptual framework of inquiring about the aesthetics of communicative structures can lead to different levels of questions.

Hadid's design can be seen as a provocative response to a climate of increasing and pervasive cultural conformity with little room for alternative ways of living. In this broad ideological context, Hadid's design, roughly speaking, proposes a new model for life. Second, we can observe how Hadid's design

proposes new orders of experiencing and meeting the world. Hadid's design contains a strong and ideologically biased idea of living differently but only expresses this idea through a physical manifestation. In short, Her design tries to lead us, "afford" us, [43] to live in new ways that could hardly be imagined *before* the realization and presentation of the design. In this sense, his design also encompasses a dimension of *performatively* implying an irreversibility of a "before" and "after"—the way we think of and experience design can never be quite the same again. Thus, it performs the new kind of being that it states on an ideological level. In and through its physical manifestation, Hadid's design not only suggests an idea of living differently, it fundamentally challenges our very understanding of design.

4. Working with Aesthetics in Design

The paper argues that aesthetics in design is a matter of how design relates to meaning. It is not enough to ask *what* the meaning of a specific design is on a conceptual level (the "idea"), we must also ask how it performs or reflects this meaning in its physical form, and how it relates to the kind of selfreflective "aesthetic function" where it displays a surplus of meaning.

In this way, discussing aesthetics in design is a way of consciously focusing on dimensions of meaning in design, but also, on behalf of the designers, on the construction of meaning. How can a surplus of meaning be invested in design, and how can it be reflected in an actual piece of design?

Hadid points to one possible direction in allowing the basic idea to be so pervasive and effective in her design that it not only stands behind the sensual relation of creating an ambience but also produces a surplus of meaning on an ideological level of a different way of life. This principle can be observed in a series of chairs by the Karim Rashid (2008). Two of them have the same shape, (Figure 5) and (Figure 6); the third, (Figure 7) is a little different, but started from the same form.

Figure 5 Rashid's Blobulous Chairs, 2008

Figure 6 Rashid's Ouch Chair, 2009

Figure7 Rashid's Loveseat, 2006

With the same form, all three chairs can be seen as mediators of the same principle. The construction is based on two identical. Viewed as a continuous series, the chairs represent an ongoing meditation on—and a perfection of a principle of—construction where the latest, *Ouch Chair*, stand as the current culmination. [44] Rashid's chairs represent a play with material and form: the form does not rationally follow the functional aspects of being a chair made for sitting; instead, it follows the experimental principle of the form. In this sense, the chairs are attempts at bringing a rather abstract idea to life. The idea, however, does not remain abstract but is (as with most design) sensuously laid out in concrete materials, demanding a place in actual space.

Normally, the sensuous qualities of design produce the “extra” element of the design that is often regarded as “aesthetic.”

As with Hadid, the idea pervades and determines the design, and in both cases there is an almost perfect integration of idea and physical manifestation—the idea is only relevant in so far as it is “put to work,” and the physical expression of form has hardly any relevance without an idea or meaning content. In my view, this is a hallmark of aesthetics in design. But where Hadid's design reflectively points to the fact that there is some kind of idea operating in and through the design (clearly evident in the way her design, appealing directly and aggressively to the senses, performs the utopian idea of a different way of life), in Rashid's chairs the idea is a more subtle, pure form experiment. This structure of investigating how an idea can be reflected in the design and how it can create a surplus of meaning (that is, the overall aesthetic question of *how* design relates to meaning on a general level) can not only be described in design, it can also be used more actively (by designers) as a tool of reflection in the design process.

In relating these two aspects of design as aesthetics of communicative self-reflection, where the x-axis represents the relation to the “aesthetic function,” (that is, the degree of surplus of meaning in relation to functional qualities) and the y-axis represents the reflection of the idea, it is possible to see how different kinds of design communicate differently aesthetically. This coordinate system encompasses *different modes* of aesthetics:

Framework for conceiving aesthetics in design as the formulation and construction of meaning

Way of reflecting the idea

Figure 8 Framework

”functionality” is not opposed to ”aesthetics” as such but according to the two axes has its own kind of aesthetics with a non-surplus in the appearance of the sensuous relation. Designs in this category include the purely functional design of everyday objects that may also reflect the idea content in different ways. At one end of the spectrum there is *anonymous* design, where we simply see through the inherent idea; at the other end of the spectrum there is the kind of *functional* design that displays its idea in a way that only reflects that there *is* an idea but which also, through this mechanism, often explains itself in a process of ”natural mapping.” [45] Likewise, there can be (as described in the cases of Rashid and Hadid) different modes of aesthetics linked to a great surplus of meaning and appearance. At one end of the spectrum there is the purely conceptual design, which does not, however, entirely circumscribe the modality of Hadid’s highly sensuous experiments, but which is prevalent when the conceptual aspect is formulated on the ideological level. The other end of the spectrum is where most ”life style” design is found, a type of design that uses a high degree of outer appearance with a surplus of appeal to the users, or rather consumers, and where it is not important that the underlying idea is reflectively stated. Rashid’s design is more experimental than ”life style, but she operates with the same approach of indirectly putting the idea to work. The experimental focus of his series of chairs is to *challenge* the relation of idea and physical manifestation so that the idea does not take over but has the status of Merleau-Ponty’s inner structure, manifesting and hiding itself at the same time. In Rashid’s case, aesthetics in design is expressed as an ongoing dialogue of outer appearance, constantly hiding and revealing its meaning content.

5. Conclusion

The theoretical framework proposed here can be used in analyses and discussions of aesthetics in design, but it can also inform designers who need to deal practically with the challenges of the aesthetic in design. The two aspects of aesthetics in design that are put forward in this paper—design as a structure of sensual appearance, and design as an act of communication that may contain an aesthetic coding that lets an idea

or content of meaning be physically manifested and reflected in different ways—can lead to a more theoretically focused inclusion of aesthetic matters in the process of designing.

Thus, it will be concluded by indicating how the questions raised in this paper can be turned into a series of aesthetic challenges for designers. The first issue is the challenge to work consciously and strategically with the *sensuous* impact of design, that is, to draw specific attention to the nature and function of the sensual when designing. In this way, the concept of “ambience” can become an important addition to the toolbox of design methodology. Further, we may consider how an object can be designed to urge a kind of “enhanced perception.” This does not, however, necessarily mean that design needs to flash and mark itself as “design;” it can also be accomplished in the anonymous design of everyday objects through more subtle aesthetics and a more discreet appearance. However, it may prove productive to challenge the aim and scope of design and its means of creating an entire universe of sensuality, as demonstrated in the case of Hadid’s design, where the power and importance of a sensual relation are achieved through designerly means.

In sum, these instruments can be used as an aesthetic challenge to the conventional way of conceiving design and the means by which it is created, thus facilitating the overall development of designerly and practical means of addressing aesthetics in design.

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